

Data format for TWOSEX-MSChart
 TWOSEX-MSChart生命表資料格式

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You have to collect 1. Stage developmental duration of each individual. 2. sex of each individual. 3. Daily fecundity of all females.

No.	Sex	Developmental duration				Daily fecundity								
		Egg	Larva	Pupa	Adult	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	M	6	11	12	6									
2	F	6	10	11	10	0	124	12	0	4	2			
3	F	6	11	10	10	0	22	74	13	0	1			
4	F	6	12	10	7	0	97	28	1	4	0			
5	M	6	12	11	5									
6	F	6	12	11	14	0	61	11	7	15	15	2	3	4
7	M	6	13	10	8									
..									
16	F	6	13	11	9	100	17	45	8					
..									
19	N	6	13	-8										
20	N	6	-10											

Lines of basic information of life table data

“Project: Diamondback moth at 25C”
 “User: Ta-Chi Yang”
 “DBM”
 50
 3,7
 F, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Female
 M, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Male
 N, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Unknown
 L1,L4

Explanation

“Project: Diamondback moth at 25C” (Project)
 “User: Ta-Chi Yang” (User name)
 “DBM” (Treatment code) This line is critical.
 50 (Number of eggs used at the beginning)
 3,7 (Number of types, number of stages)
 F, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Female (Female stages)
 M, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Male (Male stages)
 N, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Unknown (Unknown type)
 L1,L4 (Special grouping from L1 to L4)

Detailed explanation of data format

"Project: Diamondback moth at 25C"
 "User: Ta-Chi Yang"
 "DBM."
 50 **(Number of eggs used at the beginning)**
 3,7 **(Number of types, number of stages)**
 F, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Female **(Female stages)**
 M, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Male **(Male stages)**
 N, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Unknown **(Unknown type)**
L1,L4 (Special grouping: total time from L1 to L4)
 1,M,7,3,4,5,6,5,8 **(Developmental time)**
 2,F,7,2,3,4,5,8,6,4,12,9,5,8,0,-1 **(Daily fecundity)**
 3,N,7,-7 **(Died on 7th day of L1)**
 4,F,6,2,3,4,5,7,19,0,0,2,20,9,6,5,10,8,13,10,12,9,0,0,-1

Don't use "" or any non-ASCII code. 勿用中文。

Write data for individuals no. 1 and 2

1,M,6,11,12,6
 2,F,6,10,11,10,0,124,12,0,4,2,0,0,0,0,-1
 or
 1,M,6,11,12,6
 2,F,6,10,11,10,0,124,12,0,4,2,-1
 or
 1,M,6,11,12,6
 2,F,6,10,11,10
 0,124,12,0,4,2,-1

Ending zeros are omitted. 省略尾端的0.

Developmental time and fecundity in separate lines, especially when the reproduction period is very long. 繁殖期若很長，可將繁殖率另寫數行。

Data format for 7 developmental stages

Descriptive data and definition

Developmental time for each individual and fecundity for each female.

```

"Project: Silverleaf whitefly at 25C"
"User: Hsin Chi"
"25C" → Don't use "°C".
50
3,7
F, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Female
M, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Male
N, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Unknown
L1,L4 → This line asks the program to calculate the total larval duration.
1,M,7,3,4,5,6,5,8
2,F,7,2,3,4,5,8,6,4,12,9,5,8,0,-1
3,N,7,-7
4,F,.....
                    
```

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Data format for 2 developmental stages

Descriptive data and definition

Developmental time for each individual and fecundity for each female

```

"Project: Silverleaf whitefly at 30C"
"User: Hsin Chi"
"30C" → Treatment code. As short as possible!
50
3,2
F, Immature, Female
M, Immature, Male
N, Immature, Unknown
Immature, Female → You must have this line.
1,M,30,8
2,F,29,6,4,12 → Individuals died in immature stages are N type!
3,N,-7
4,F,.....
                    
```

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Data format for Parthenogenetic populations
孤雌生殖種群資料格式

Descriptive data and definition

Developmental time for each individual and fecundity for each female

"Aphis gossypii"
"Shally"
"25C" → **Treatment code. As short as possible!**
56
2,5
F,N1,N2,N3,N4,Female
N,N1,N2,N3,N4,Unknown
N1,N4

1,F,2,1,3,1,18,0,9,0,11,12, ..., -1
.....
48,N,1,3,-1 → **Individuals died in immature stages are N type!**
.....

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Data format for Parthenogenetic populations
孤雌生殖種群資料格式 (三種型: F, M, N)

Descriptive data and definition

Developmental time for each individual and fecundity for each female

"Aphis gossypii"
"Shally"
"25C"
56
3,5
F,N1,N2,N3,N4,Female
M,N1,N2,N3,N4,Male ← **It is OK to write this line. 沒有雄蟲仍可以寫這一行**
N,N1,N2,N3,N4,Unknown
N1,N4

1,F,2,1,3,1,18,0,9,0,11,12, ..., -1
.....
48,N,1,3,-1
.....

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Data format for 7 developmental stages with stage-specific rearing cost (含飼養費用之資料)

"Project: Diamondback moth at 25C"

"User: Hsin Chi"

"DBM."

50

3,7

F, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Female

M, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Male

N, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Unknown

0, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 0, 2, 1.5

L1,L4

The rearing cost for egg, L1, L2, L3, L4, Pupa, Female and Male adults are 0, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 0, 2, and 1.5, respectively.

Not well! There are 8 data. 2 is the rearing cost of female and 1.5 is the cost of male.

資料格式：7 發育階段與飼養費用

"Project: Diamondback moth at 25C"

"User: Hsin Chi"

"DBM"

50

3,7

F, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Female

M, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Male

N, Egg, L1,L2,L3,L4,Pupa,Unknown

0, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 0, 2, 1.5

L1,L4

注意：有8個飼養費用。最後兩個是雌雄成蟲的飼養費用。

The rearing cost for egg, L1, L2, L3, L4, Pupa, Female and Male adults are 0, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 0, 2, and 1.5, respectively.

Attention!

Do NOT enter more than 30 data items in each line. Press ENTER at the end of each line.

建議：每行不要超過30個資料

理由：容易閱讀與偵錯

請用 **WordPad**, **Notepad** 寫生命表資料
如果使用 NotePad 產生錯誤，建議使用 WordPad.

Use pure text editors: **WordPad, Notepad** to prepare your data file

If you collect life table data every 0.5 day

No.	Sex	Developmental duration (day)				Fecundity (every 0.5 day)								
		Egg	Larva	Pupa	Adult	0.5	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5
1	M	3.5	5.5	6.5	6									
2	F	5.0	9.0	4.5	12	20	104	6	7	8	9			
..									

You have to write the number of time units for developmental times. The fecundity data should be recorded every 0.5 day.

1,M,7,11,13,12

2,F,10,18,9,24,20,104,6,7,8,9,.....,-1

Your time unit is “0.5”.

Time unit: 1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.25, 0.2, 0.16...

When you see the following message,
please enter the time unit for your data

If you collect life table data every 8 hour

No.	Sex	Developmental duration (hour)				Fecundity (every 8 hour)								
		Egg	Larva	Pupa	Adult	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64	72
1	M	16	24	72	80									
2	F	8	32	64	56	20	104	6	7	8	9			
..									

You have to write the number of time units for developmental times. The fecundity data should be recorded every 8 hour.

1,M,2,3,9,10

2,F,1,4,8,7,20,104,6,7,8,9,.....,-1

Your time unit is "0.3".

Time unit: 1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.25, 0.2, 0.16...

When you see the following message,
please enter the time unit for your data

Teşekkür ederim!

سپاسگزارم

謝謝!

ขอบคุณครับ

Děkuji

Danke!

Grazie!

Obrigado!

¡Muchas gracias!

Thank you!

ご清聴ありがとうございます!